

Description of rice varieties and lines previously reported to be at least moderately resistant to RHBV, their ancestors, and percentage of plants with RHBV symptoms.

Name	Origin	Designation	Cross	Reaction to RHBV (% of affected plants)
<i>Varieties and lines</i>				
Colombia 1	Colombia	T319E-2M-2M-1M-1M	Napal/Takao Iku 18	3.9
Diamante	Chile	P1-2-2-2-1	Agostano/Blue Rose//Balilla	3.8
ICA10	Colombia	T112D-7P-5T	British Guyana 79/(PI215936 × CI9124)	2.2
INIAP415	Ecuador	P1042-2-3-1B	P738-137-4/P723-40-3-1	28.0
—	IRRI	IR1721-146-4-3	IR24*3/O. <i>nivara</i>	72.9
Lacrosse	USA	Sel. no. 250-121	2913A5-1-3/AL11-1	7.4
Oryzica 1	Colombia	P1429-8-9M-1B	P1223/P1225	23.6
Oryzica Llanos 4	Colombia	P5413-8-3-5-11	CR 1113/IRAT 122//Colombia1/P1274-6-8M	4.4
Oryzica Llanos 5	Colombia	CT5747-24-5-4-2	Colombia 1/P1274-6-8M*2//P2060F4-25-2	0.8
<i>Parents</i>				
Agostano	Italy	Acc. 3135	—	0.7
Agostano	Hungary	Acc. 9334	—	61.7
Balilla	Italy	Acc. 3098	—	88.3
Balilla	Italy	Acc. 3107	—	6.4
Blue Rose	USA	Acc. 1731	—	8.3
Blue Rose	USA	Acc. 1732	—	0.9
IR24	Philippines	IR661-1-140-3	IR8/IR127-2-2	78.5
<i>Oryza nivara</i>	India	Acc. 101508	—	97.9
PI215936	China	Acc. 146	—	3.7
PI215936/CI9214	USA	Acc. 11394	—	6.1
Takao Iku 18	China	Acc. 3037	—	5.7
Takao Iku 18	China	Acc. 6923	—	6.6
<i>Other ancestors</i>				
B5580AL-1-15 (CP-SLO)	USA	Acc. 6993	Century Patna/SLO 17	83.3
Chianan 8	China	Acc. 90	Taichung 65//Mitsui/Oloan-chu	19.8
Colusa	USA	Acc. 1714	—	3.3
Fortuna	USA	Acc. 1708	—	62.5
Makaloka	Madagascar	—	—	13.0
Sigadis	Indonesia	Acc. 5324	Bluebonnet/Benong	75.6
Taichung 65	China	Acc. 79	Shinriki/Kameji	2.0
<i>Checks</i>				
Colombia 1 (resistant)	Colombia	T319E-2M-2M-1M-1M	Napal/Takao Iku 18	5.0
Bluebonnet 50 (susceptible)	USA	—	Rexoro/Fortuna	83.6

Detection of rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) in asymptomatic leaves of tungro-infected rice plants by polymerase chain reaction (PCR)

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We have detected the presence of RTBV and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) in infected TN1 rice plants by antibody fragment F(ab')₂ enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) 1 wk after

inoculation. Green leafhoppers *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant) were given an acquisition access period of 72 h on plants infected with both rice tungro disease (RTD) viruses and a transmission access period of 24 h on 2-wk-old rice seedlings (2 d-leaf stage). Infected plants were grouped, following F(ab')₂ ELISA tests, for the presence of RTSV (S) or RTBV (B) alone or RTD (B+S) in the newly emerged leaf. RTD-infected rice seedlings were dissected 1 wk after inoculation (3 d-leaf stage) into individual leaves, stem apex, and roots. Each part was then tested for the presence of RTSV or RTBV by F(ab')₂ ELISA and for the presence of RTBV DNA by PCR.

The presence of viral coat proteins varied in different plant parts (Fig. 1). One wk after inoculation, detectable amounts of RTSV and RTBV viral coat proteins were found in the newly emerged leaf (leaf 3), stem apex, and roots.

Among the symptomless leaves (those which emerged before the insect inoculation), very few (3 out of 20) contained detectable amounts of RTSV coat proteins. Neither virus was detectable by F(ab')₂ ELISA in most of them. Two plants showing a typical pattern of virus distribution by F(ab')₂ ELISA (Fig. 1c) were dissected and tested by PCR (Fig. 1d). PCR showed the presence of RTBV DNA in symptomless leaves of these plants.

In RTD-infected plants, RTBV DNA was detected in all parts of the infected plant by PCR. The PCR technique is much more sensitive than F(ab')₂ ELISA for

detecting the presence of RTBV in symptomatic and symptomless plant tissue.

Oligonucleotide primers were designed to the published sequence of RTBV. The

1. Viral coat proteins in different plant parts as detected by ELISA and PCR.

[#]1 and 2 = leaves emerged before insect inoculation; 3 = newly emerged leaf after insect inoculation; NV = no virus (es) detected; B = RTBV; S = RTSV; B + S = RTBV + RTSV.

²20 RTD-infected plants were dissected into five parts (leaves 1, 2, and 3, stem apex, and roots). ^cOut of 20 RTD-infected plants, dissected parts of two plants were tested by PCR.

plus strand primer (5'-GAG-CGCTGATTACCCAACCTTTCAAGG-3') and minus strand primer (5'-GGA-GTAGAATACTCCACAACCGGCG-3') were complementary to regions of the P12 and P194 open reading frames, respectively, and amplified an 827-bp fragment of RTBV DNA. PCR reaction conditions were standard with a typical input of 100 ng of total nucleic acid extract of rice plant tissue and 50 nM primers. PCR reaction products were resolved on 1% agarose gels stained with ethidium bromide (Fig. 2). ■

2. PCR products resolved in 1% agarose gel stained with ethidium bromide. Markers: lane 1 = uninfected extract; lane 2 = no DNA; lanes 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7 = extracts from stem apex, dissected leaves no. 3, 2, 1, and roots.

Evaluation of resistance to bakanae and foot rot disease

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Bakanae and foot rot disease, caused by *Fusarium moniliforme* Sheld., appeared in patches on Basmati 385 in farmers' fields during 1989. The disease developed further because no control measures were adopted. None of the Basmati 385 fields surveyed during 1991 were disease-free in Sheikhupura, Gujranwala, and Sialkot districts, which make up the traditional rice-growing area in the Punjab. Disease incidence ranged from 5 to 90%.

To overcome the disease problem through resistant varieties, 10 fine-grain and 10 medium-grain varieties/lines were screened in the greenhouse during 1990-92. Soil was infected with the diseased plant debris and *F. moniliforme* culture grown on wheat grains. During 1990 and 1992, the inoculum potential

Reaction of rice varieties/lines to bakanae and foot rot disease under greenhouse conditions.

Variety	Disease incidence (%)		
	1990	1991	1992
<i>Fine grain</i>			
Basmati 370	16.7	92.4	15.40
Basmati 6129	8.3	77.0	69.20
Basmati 198	0.0	38.5	54.6
Basmati 385	58.3	84.7	46.2
4048	50.0	100.0	61.5
1053-32	-	92.4	0.0
4439	-	15.4	0.0
1053-1-2	-	84.7	7.7
33608	-	100.0	7.7
Basmati C-622	16.7	100.0	46.2
<i>Medium grain</i>			
Shadab	0.0	0.0	0.0
Iran	-	92.4	30.8
PK3303-15-1	-	0.0	0.0
DR83	0.0	30.8	0.0
Jhona 349	-	100.0	38.5
IR8	-	0.0	0.0
IR6	0.0	7.7	0.0
IR9	0.0	0.0	0.0
KS282	0.0	0.0	0.0
PK1399-12-1-1-0-6	0.0	7.7	0.0